

DESIGN AND TESTING OF LIGHT-WEIGHT PARTICLE FILLED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The goal of the study is to find a cost effective composition of particle-reinforced composite that is light but has advanced mechanical properties.

The matrix of the particulate composite is unsaturated polyester resin (UP) that is reinforced with alumina trihydrate (ATH) powder. Part of the ATH proportion was replaced with hollow glass microspheres to reduce weight.

In order to find out the influence of the light filler to the composites physical and mechanical properties tests with different percentage of the light filler were conducted. Based on the test data a multi-criteria optimisation problem has been formulated and solved. The optimal solution is given as Pareto curve, to represent the distinction between the weight and selected mechanical properties of the composite structure.

1. Introduction

Particulate composite material consisting of unsaturated polyester resin (UP) and alumina trihydrate (ATH) shows good mechanical and physical properties. The material is used for fabricating counter-tops, sanitary-ware and furniture. The use of the material is limited in some applications because of its weight and cost. Lighter weight would decrease the transportation cost, enable to produce larger products and make the handling and installation easier. Several solutions have been used to overcome these problems. A variety of different light weight fillers have been added to particulate composites in order to achieve weight savings. For example polymethylmetacrylate (PMMA) powder [1], hollow glass microspheres [2]

and silicate based light weight particulate fillers [3]. Microscopic hollow soda-lime-borosilicate spheres are low-density particles that are used in a wide range of industries. The hollow microspheres are used to reduce warpage and shrinkage, to adjust the rheological properties, to reduce part weight and to lower cost. On the other hand the increased concentration of light-weight particulate reinforcement like micro balloon can decrease the mechanical properties of the particle filled composite material [4]. If the filler is less resistant to penetration then the thermoset matrix it will lower the indentation hardness of the composite [5].

The goal of the current study is to find out cost effective material composition that is light in weight but has sufficient mechanical properties.

The procedure developed for solving posed problem includes:

- design of experiment,
- conduction of experimental study for determining mechanical and physical properties of the material prepared with different filler ratios,
- response modelling,
- multi-criteria optimisation.

The evaluation of the objective functions from experimental data is time consuming, too expensive and thus not reasonable. A common technique for reducing time resources and minimizing cost in optimal design problems is to use surrogate models for the approximation of the objective and constraint functions.

There are a number of surrogate model types available, with applications in different areas ranging from sociology to space [6-7]. Most widely used types of surrogate models include Artificial

Neural Networks (ANN), Radial Basis Function models, Rational Functions, Support Vector Machines, Kriging models, etc. In the current study, the artificial neural networks are used for the modelling of response surfaces, corresponding to different mechanical properties of the composite material. Multicriteria optimisation problem is formulated on the basis of analysis of the relationships between mechanical properties of the material. Finally, the solution of multicriteria optimization problem was obtained by applying Pareto optimality concept and methodology introduced by authors in [8-9].

2. Experimental study

There are a number of physical and mechanical properties that characterises a polymeric composite. The most demonstrative properties to observe the effect of fillers are tensile strength, indentation hardness, flexural strength, flexural modulus and impact strength.

In the current study the percentage of the light filler, the resin - ATH ratio and post curing temperature are considered as design variables. Design of experiment has been performed by varying the values of these parameters. In order to find out the influence of design variables on the mechanical properties of the composite the different material compositions were prepared and tested.

Test specimens were cut from molded sheets, which were produced by using vacuum assisted extruder-type mixing equipment. Preliminary cure of the composite was done at room temperature ($23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) for 12 h. That was followed by post cure in conventional thermal oven. Tensile tests of the composite plastic materials were performed according to standard ISO 527-1:2000. The flexural properties of the material were determined by 3 point bending test as specified in ISO 178. The indentation hardness of the material was measured with GYZJ 934-1 Barcol impressor according to ASTM D 2583-99. For obtaining reference values also material without light weight filler was tested.

3. Modeling of light-weight particle filled polymer composite

Let us proceed from a predetermined set of designs obtained from experimental study. In the following, the output data obtained from the tests are treated as response values. The artificial neural networks (ANNs) are used for the surface fitting. The surface

constructed by the use of NNs does not normally contain the given response values (similarity with the least-squares method in this respect).

Based on test data, the relationship between the mechanical properties of the material (output data) and design variables (light filler, resin-ATH filler ratio and post curing temperature) has been established.

Analysing the behaviour of the mechanical properties considered one can conclude that:

- the mechanical properties describing general stiffness/strength characteristics of the material (tensile strength, bending stress, elongation, modulus of elasticity) have similar behaviour with respect to design variables and can be grouped into one group of properties. The reduced order model can be obtained by selecting one of these properties to represent this group (e.g. tensile strength),
- the surface hardness has similar behaviour with mechanical properties responsible for general stiffness/strength characteristics, but its physical meaning is a quite different (it is responsible rather for local characteristics),
- contradictory behaviour can be perceived between the tensile strength and material density, also between the surface hardness and material density.

To precede form analysis done so far, the multicriteria optimisation problem is formulated on the following basis:

- the three different objectives considered are the tensile strength, surface hardness and material density,
- two objectives - tensile strength and surface hardness are combined into one objective employing the weighted summation (or compromise programming) technique.

The relationship between the two combined criteria and material density can be determined by use of Pareto optimality concept. Such an approach allows obtaining 2D Pareto front.

According to the weighted summation technique, all the criteria combined are scaled, multiplied by weights and summed into the general objective f_1 as

$$f_1 = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i f_{1i}, \quad (1)$$

where m is the number of the optimality criteria used, w_i is the weight of the i -th criteria and

$$\sum_{i=1}^m w_i = 1, \quad 0 < w_i \leq 1. \quad (2)$$

In latter case $m = 2$ and scaling of the objectives can be performed as

$$f_{11}(x) = \frac{\max T_S(\bar{x}) - T_S(\bar{x})}{\max T_S(\bar{x}) - \min T_S(\bar{x})},$$

$$f_{12}(x) = \frac{\max S_H(\bar{x}) - S_H(\bar{x})}{\max S_H(\bar{x}) - \min S_H(\bar{x})}, \quad (3)$$

where T_S and S_H stand for the tensile strength and surface hardness, respectively and \bar{x} is vector of design variables. Scaling of the third optimality criterion, material density, is little different,

$$f_2(x) = \frac{M_T(\bar{x}) - \min M_T(\bar{x})}{\max M_T(\bar{x}) - \min M_T(\bar{x})}, \quad (4)$$

since it is subjected to minimization (first two objectives, the tensile strength and surface hardness are subjected to maximization). In (4) M_T stands for the material density. As result, there are two objective functions f_1 and f_2 subjected to minimization and given by formulas (1)-(4).

Thus, the multi-criteria optimisation problem can be formulated as

$$f(\bar{x}) = \min(f_1(\bar{x}), f_2(\bar{x})) \quad (5)$$

subjected to linear constraints

$$x_i \leq x_i^*, \quad -x_i \leq x_{i*}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (6)$$

and non-linear constraints

$$\sigma(\bar{x}) \leq \sigma^*. \quad (7)$$

In (6) x_i^* and x_{i*} stand for the upper and lower bounds of the design variables, respectively. The non-linear constraints (7) is imposed on stress σ and requires that it does not exceed the given limit value σ^* .

4. Experimental results

One of the most important characteristics, the tensile strength of the composite material depends from the

adhesion strength between the matrix and the reinforcement material [5, 10]. The results of tensile tests can be seen from Figure 1. Another prominent physical effect the indentation hardness is largely influenced by the modulus of matrix and filler. The filler is less resistant to penetration than the matrix in this case and the indentation hardness decreases as depicted in Figure 2. As can be observed from Figure 3 the light filler has positive effect on the weight reduction by lowering the density.

5. Numerical results

An analysis and simplifications done in section 3 allows obtaining of the reduced order model which contains two optimality criteria. The Pareto front of the combined objectives (1) and material density (4) is given in Fig. 4.

First note, that increase of the values of the combined objective $f_1(\bar{x})$ means that distance of the tensile strength and surface hardness from its maximal values increases, thus the values of the tensile strength and surface hardness are decreasing. It can be seen from Fig. 4, that relation between these two objectives is described by Pareto curve consisting from two linear parts (can be approximated as linear). Reducing of the material density function $f_2(\bar{x})$ from 0.76 up to 0.43 leads to proportional decrease of the combined function (from tensile strength and surface hardness), further reduction of the material density function leads to much faster reduction of the combined function. The optimal solution for posed optimization problem can be selected as intersection point of two linear parts of the Pareto curve, but not necessarily. In general, the selection of an optimal solution is still complicated and depends on a number of factors, like the specific problem considered, additional information available, etc [11, 12].

The Pareto front of the objective functions does contain more information than the physical programming approaches. The shape of the Pareto front provides valuable information.

It can be mentioned that, that simplifications done in section 3 are based on analysis and can be affirmed by simulations with more complex models.

In order to achieve higher accuracy the real-coded genetic algorithm is employed. In a standard formulation the genetic algorithm may converge close to an optimal solution not to optimal solution. The refined algorithm has been proposed for design improvement - hybrid GA. A global-local approach

for the optimization has been employed [13, 14]. The hybrid approach used provides a global search with the GA and was subsequently further refined with a gradient-based search. The function approximation and optimization modules are realized in MATLAB and C++ programming environment.

Conclusions

A new composite is modelled on the basis of testing the material. The mechanical properties of experimentally manufactured composite materials were tested.

Numerical procedure has been developed for design the new composite. Artificial neural networks and real-coded genetic algorithm (GA) were used for modelling response between objectives and design variables and solving optimization problem, respectively.

An analysis of the candidates for objective functions has been performed and reduced order model was developed. The mechanical properties responsible for global stiffness/strength of the material are grouped and replaced by one representative objective function.

Composite material filled with 6 % of microballons showed 3 % loss in the tensile strength and 26 % loss in the indentation hardness compared to the composition without it. The weight decrease can be estimated up to 13 % from the initial composition. In conclusion, one can say that it is possible to find a compromise between lower density and loss in mechanical properties when using hollow glass microspheres as additional filler in particulate reinforced composite material.

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Fig. 1. Density, g/cm³

Fig. 2. Tensile strength, MPa

Fig. 3. Barcol hardness

Fig. 4. The combined objective $f_1(\bar{x})$ versus material density $f_2(\bar{x})$

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